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Flexibility Service for Balance Responsible Parties' Industrial Customers: A Day-Ahead Cost Optimization Approach Using Price Forecasting

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ABSTRACT Electricity-intensive industries are highly impacted by electricity prices and their fluctuations. While these industries can change their consumption profiles to avoid peak price periods, they must also adhere to production schedules dictated by their unique manufacturing processes and related constraints. Balance Responsible Parties (BRPs), seek to optimize the electricity costs of their portfolio of customers and have limited access to real-time industrial flexibility. So, the concept of Daily Industrial Flexibility (DIF) is introduced as a trade-off between real-time flexibility and predetermined industrial schedules. Each factory can propose different fixed day-ahead consumption profiles to the BRP, each with a specific activation cost. In this context, this paper proposes a day-ahead flexibility service to minimize the BRP's costs of electricity purchase on the day-ahead market, activating DIFs within the portfolio of industrial customers. A forecasting model for the electricity price is implemented and an optimization model is formulated to minimize day-ahead portfolio costs. Finally, the case study of a Catalan BRP is presented, considering DIF offers from its largest customers. Results demonstrate that the proposed approach enables accurate predictions of the BRP's customers operation before DAM closure, successfully identifying alternative schedules to reduce portfolio costs.

INDEX TERMS Balance responsible party, day-ahead market, day-ahead optimization, demand response, electricity markets, electricity price forecasting, flexibility services.

I. INTRODUCTION

The climate crisis demonstrates how essential it is to integrate Renewable Energy Sources (RES) in order to obtain a decarbonised energy sector [1], with decisive goals set to decrease emissions [2]. The integration of RES, however, is not a straightforward process [3]. It introduces several operational complications in electric power systems [4] due to variable generation patterns [5], unreliable long

term forecasts [3], need for increased power generation reserves [6] and overall power quality challenges [7]. This leads to higher price volatility in electricity markets [8], with consequences for multiple stakeholders involved. This phenomenon has been widely studied for different countries, with [9] studying RES induced electricity price volatility in the United States, [10] in the Iberian market and [11] in Germany and Denmark.

Well documented in literature, flexibility has been noted as a possible solution to support grids with high penetration of RES [12]. To this extent, in [13] and [14] and [15]

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power system flexibility sources and products are reviewed. Although not uniquely defined, it is intended as the possibility of modifying generation and/or consumption patterns in reaction to an external signal in order to provide valuable services within the energy system [16]. The closer to real time operations these changes can be made, the higher the value of the provided service [17].

In this context, Day-Ahead Market (DAM) price forecasting plays a crucial role in aiding flexibility integration [18]. Indeed, predictions of future electricity prices allow market participants to better plan their generation and consumption strategies [19], [20]. In the case of flexibility providers, price forecasts enable them to determine the most opportune moments to offer services, improving their ability to respond to market needs [21].

Balance Responsible Parties (BRPs) are among the key stakeholders in electricity market that can benefit from day-ahead flexibility provision to contrast RES-induced volatility [22]. According to the European Commission, a BRP is defined as a market participant or its designated representative responsible for managing its imbalances [23]. Operationally, they are financially responsible towards the Transmission System Operator (TSO) for adhering to a declared energy schedule, comprised of multiple consumption and generation assets across different grid access points. In order to guarantee this balance between generation and consumption within their portfolio and to minimise the costs, they sell and purchase on energy markets with different time scales. BRPs trade electricity through futures contracts months or years ahead of schedule to cover long term baseload needs. Then, closer to the time of delivery, the final schedule is decided trading on the DAM. When necessary, final adjustments are made exchanging electricity in the more expensive intra-day markets [24].

The value of industrial demand-side flexibility is known, and plays a crucial role in shaping the future of the electricity system [25]. Demand Response (DR) programmes encourage factories to decrease or shift electrical consumption when the electrical system is under stress in exchange for monetary remuneration [26], [27]. Indeed, efforts are increasingly focused on expanding industrial flexibility via the integration of cyber-physical components, enhancing automation, and overall efficiency [28]. Avoiding peak prices periods is crucial to operate profitably, yet real time adjustments and participation in flexibility provision are not guaranteed, as discussed in [29]. Studies such as [30] consider energy systems optimization with day-ahead and real time coordination, but do not mention limitations for industrial participation. The right tariffs and incentives need to be in place to convince industries to change how they manage energy [31].

Demand-side flexibility programmes are usually classified in two groups: implicit (or price-based) and explicit (or incentive-based) [32], [33]. Implicit DR programmes rely on consumers voluntarily modifying their consumption patterns, in response to market price signals. For example, in Time

of Use (ToU) tariffs a day is divided in three time intervals, each characterized by a different price. As a consequence, consumers are encouraged to favour consumption during the cheaper time intervals. Explicit DR, on the other hand, involves customers receiving financial remuneration for modifying their load by a specific amount within a predefined activation window.

Industrial participation to DR, however, is limited by barriers of both regulatory and technical nature. Regulatory barriers such as high minimum bid size, notification time, or required response time may limit the amount of DR energy industries can provide, as covered in [34]. On the other hand, as identified in [35], technical barriers are dictated by the lack of flexibility of manufacturing process schedules. Indeed, schedules are optimized to ensure product quality maintaining continuous operation, and to meet other key requirements such as safety and cost-efficiency. This makes dynamic electricity consumption adjustments difficult.

Price forecasting and day-ahead flexibility optimization have been widely investigated in the past decade, however limited research is present on day-ahead aggregated flexibility for industrial customers of BRPs. A day-ahead intelligent energy management strategy for manufacturing load participation in DR is suggested in [36], but only focuses on one industry and does not consider aggregation within BRP portfolios. [37] proposes a framework for day-ahead portfolio optimization by combining DAM trading with aggregated flexibility requests, but does not present a case study. Similarly, [38] provides a review of power system flexibility, mentioning the advantages of day-ahead balancing but without presenting applications. [39] presents a stochastic model for predictive control of BRPs, however focuses on real-time flexibility and does not consider industrial scheduling needs. Similarly, [40] studies possible BRP strategies for short-term flexibility, recognizing the limitation that not all BRPs can make such rapid adjustments. [41] applies a flexibility envelope approach for day-ahead scheduling and intraday dispatch coordination, however only considers alternative electricity profiles provided by micro energy systems. A Belgian BRP case study of day-ahead portfolio management is presented in [42], however focuses on applications for residential electricity consumers. Other works such as [43] and [44] present a day-ahead optimization problem solved with the Alternative Direction Method of Multipliers (ADMM) [45] algorithm formulation. The first to maximize flexibility potentials of electro-thermal heating units and the second focusing on behind the meter distributed storage units. Neither considers flexibility derived from scheduling needs are not included. In [46], a day-ahead decision making framework for a virtual power plant considering internal DR is proposed, but does not mention the constraints of industrial production processes. To the best knowledge of the authors, few studies provide a quantitative analysis of the economic benefits of flexibility services for BRPs on the day ahead regarding industrial

customer portfolios, such as the one proposed in this paper.

Stemming from the work conducted in the Horizon Europe FLEX4FACT project [47], this paper introduces the concept of Daily Industrial Flexibility (DIF), as a service for BRPs portfolio electricity costs minimization. Typically, industries operate according to a locally optimized “baseline” electricity consumption profile. However, they can propose alternative DIF schedules, each with an associated activation cost agreed upon by the BRP and the factory. These DIFs allow flexibility in energy usage without changing overall consumption, and must be declared in advance for the BRP to make necessary adjustments in the DAM. It is an offer made directly to the BRP or portfolio manager, which acts as an intermediary to the electricity market [48]. Bid size constraints, thus, are disregarded. Since DIF schedules are proposed by industries themselves, they represent planned, daily adjustments that are easier to accommodate than real-time requests. This way, as it is anticipated and activated in the day ahead, the amount of flexibility that can be offered at a reasonable cost increases, as has been demonstrated in [49]. Being industries remunerated for providing different consumption schedules to the BRP, this concept aligns closely with explicit DR programmes. However, being originated from voluntary alternative industrial planning and optimized within the BRP portfolio allows to disregard bid size constraints and activation periods, similarly to implicit DR schemes.

This work addresses this research gap by displaying the following scientific contributions:

- Definition of the concept of DIF as means of increasing the amount of available flexibility at a reasonable cost.
- Formulation of a Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) optimization model to minimize BRP costs on the day ahead, activating DIFs within its portfolio.
- Presentation of a quantitative case study of a Catalan BRP to evaluate portfolio monetary savings following DIF activation.

In addition, the present paper explains the development of an electricity price forecasting method that includes a wide set of input parameters, such as historical gas prices and variables of the Spanish electricity energy mix. This forecast is integrated into the optimization model and the impact of uncertainty is analysed in the results.

This article is structured as follows. Section II presents the methodology to develop the day-ahead forecasts, the rules of DIFs and the formulation of the BRP cost optimization problem. Section III displays the case-study of a Catalan BRP. In Section IV the results of the day-ahead price forecasts and BRP optimization are presented. Finally, in Section V, the conclusions are drawn.

II. METHODOLOGY

The proposed service consists of three main parts: the DAM electricity price forecasting model, the modeling and definition of DIFs and the BRP portfolio cost optimization. This

section outlines the methodology behind the development of these three components, with Fig. 1 providing an overview of how they interact and the associated sections of the manuscript. Firstly, Section II-A explains the step-by-step development of the DAM electricity price forecasting model, including the requirements of the input data and the needed training window, how the features are engineered and how to train and tune the models. Focusing on the modeling of the BRP's flexibility, section II-B explains the key assumptions and operational mechanisms of the concept of DIF. Finally, these two models are combined and used to pass inputs to the final BRP cost minimization model, defined in Section II-C through the formulation of a MILP optimization problem.

FIGURE 1. Overview of the key components of the BRP cost optimization flexibility service.

A. DAY-AHEAD ELECTRICITY PRICE FORECASTING MODEL

Taking into account the unique characteristics of energy trading, this section explains the procedure to predict the DAM electricity price.

1) FORECASTING WINDOW AND MARKET CONTEXT

Firstly, to develop a forecasting algorithm, it is necessary to define the forecasting window for the target variable. This window represents the time span between when forecasts are generated and the furthest point of the prediction. For this study the Spanish DAM, managed by Operador del Mercado Ibérico de Energía (OMIE) [50], is considered.

As shown in Fig. 2, OMIE requires wholesale sellers and buyers to submit their bids before gate closure at 12:00 CET. This establishes prices for the 24 hours of the next day, equal for all the market participants. Therefore, the forecasting algorithm must run before the 12:00 CET deadline, generating predictions until midnight of the next

day. This requires a forecasting window of at least 36 hours to predict 24 hourly prices for the next day.

FIGURE 2. DAM bidding operational structure, with the electricity prices for day d are set at 12:00 CET of the previous day $d-1$. [51].

2) ALGORITHM DEVELOPMENT STEPS

The following steps are followed to develop the forecasting algorithms:

- **Data collection and data cleaning:** Gather and clean the data to create the input dataset of the forecasting problem.
- **Feature engineering:** Create additional features such as lag variables and calendar features, as shown in 2.
- **Feature normalization:** Normalize all the training features to ensure that all input features contribute equally to the learning process, regardless of feature scale. StandardScaler from scikit-learn is used. The normalization is fitted on the training data and then applied to both training and testing datasets to avoid data leakage.
- **Training and testing split:** split the dataset into training and testing datasets.
- **Feature selection:** identify and limit the model to the most significant features, reducing the risk of over-fitting.
- **Model training and hyper-parameters tuning:** identify hyper-parameters combinations which guarantee better performance and train the models accordingly.
- **Model evaluation:** evaluate the performance of the model.

In this process, Recursive Feature Elimination with Cross Validation (RFECV) is employed to identify the final set of features of the models. The method works by recursively fitting a model using the full set of features, then ranks the features based on their importance in predicting the target variable. Features are progressively removed starting from the least important one, and, for each new set of features, cross-validation scores are computed. As features are removed, scores are monitored until a further removal of features does not improve nor worsen model performance. The final set is thus found.

A final step in ensuring the best forecasting capabilities of the forecasting models is the tuning of the hyper-parameters. For each of the key hyper-parameters a grid

search is performed. This is done using the GridSearchCV method from the scikit-learn library. A range of values is defined, training the model for each possible combination and selecting the optimal configuration according to statistical error metrics. In this case Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) and the Coefficient of Determination (R^2) are the metrics of choice to evaluate the goodness of fit.

Additionally, the Kernel Density Estimate (KDE) plotting function provided by the Seaborn python package [52] is used in this work to visualize the distribution of observations in the dataset, showing a continuous curve that represents the estimated probability density of the data. This curve helps to identify patterns, such as peaks, valleys, and skewness, in the underlying distribution.

For the purpose of this study, three different forecasting models are fitted and evaluated. Namely, a benchmark Multiple Linear Regression (MLR), a Support Vector Regression (SVR) and a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) models are compared. Hyper-parameters tuning can be computationally expensive, as the grid size to examine increases exponentially increasing the range or number of hyper-parameters considered. Constraints induced by the hardware used to conduct the experiments of this work will be discussed in section II-C2.

In summary, the following assumptions apply to the development of the electricity price forecasting algorithm:

- **Data Availability:** Sufficient historical electricity price data from the DAM and external features are required to train the models. The final set of features for the presented case study are shown in Table 2.
- **Forecasting Window:** The model generates 24 hourly price forecasts for the next day, based on a 36-hour forecasting window, ensuring predictions before the OMIE bidding deadline at 12:00 CET.
- **Evaluation Metrics:** MAE, RMSE, and R^2 are used to assess model accuracy and fit.
- **Feature Engineering:** Key features include lag variables and calendar features, with normalization applied to ensure comparability.
- **Model Selection & Tuning:** MLR, SVR, and MLP are used, with hyper-parameter tuning via grid search.
- **Reproducibility:** The methodology can be applied to other markets by adjusting input data (e.g., market-specific and electricity generation features) and is compatible with standard machine learning libraries.

B. DAILY INDUSTRIAL FLEXIBILITY

This study introduces the concept of DIF as mechanism through which industries can offer flexible electricity consumption schedules to the BRP managing their electricity provision. Under typical operating conditions, industries follow a “baseline” electricity consumption profile that reflects their local optimal production configuration. However with DIFs, industries can propose alternative consumption schedules for specific days, facilitating industrial demand-side flexibility.

Each DIF comes with an associated activation cost, determined by solving an internal scheduling problem. Such computations are derived from the FLEX4FACT project [47], considering the unique constraints of each production process. The BRP, responsible for purchasing electricity on the DAM to meet the needs of its portfolio, can either compensate the industry for deviating from the baseline schedule by activating a DIF or choose to maintain the baseline consumption. It is important to note that the exact methodology for calculating the activation costs is not disclosed to the BRP. Its focus lies solely on optimizing the overall portfolio costs rather than analysing internal production constraints.

The presented framework comes with the following underlying assumptions:

- **DIF offer duration:** Each DIF consumption profile is defined with hourly granularity, corresponding to the 24 electricity price signals of the day-ahead. All DIFs offered must have the same temporal duration.
- **DIF Cost Determination:** The cost associated with each DIF is derived by solving an internal scheduling problem unique to each industry. The BRP only receives the costs of each DIF, without any details of how the scheduling problem is solved.
- **Timing of DIF declarations:** DIFs must be declared one day or more in advance, allowing BRPs to make necessary portfolio adjustments before DAM closure.
- **Energy Consumption Consistency:** all DIFs have the same amount of energy consumption of the baseline profile. This simulates the fact that daily production volume should remain constant, even when flexibility is activated.
- **Mandatory DIF Activation:** Once a DIF profile is chosen by the BRP, it is assumed that the industry is obligated to activate it, ensuring the planned flexibility is effectively delivered.
- **Fairness of DIF Activation Costs:** It is assumed that each cost is fair and accurately reflects the actual expenses incurred by industries when modifying their consumption profiles. Data falsification and verification of whether these costs are truthfully declared is beyond the scope of this study.
- **Stochastic Elements of Consumption:** The model assumes that industries have high accuracy in predicting their electricity consumption schedules. As a result, stochastic elements, such as customer demand deviations or uncertainties in industrial processes, are not considered. The electricity consumption modeled corresponds to a planned, pre-determined schedule with low variability, thus neglecting the potential randomness typically associated with customer behavior.

In the presented service, industries are compensated directly for offering consumption schedules to the BRP, which then optimizes his electricity consumption portfolio on the DAM. This approach shares characteristics with both implicit and explicit conventional DR programs,

of which [35] provides a classification and analyses their attractiveness for industrial applications. Compared to these programmes, DIF can be classified as a hybrid scheme, combining aspect of both implicit and explicit DR.

The control of flexibility activation, for example, shares aspects with both categories. Indeed, while DIF activation is implicitly carried out by the industries through the activation costs of each alternative profile, market access is explicitly guaranteed by the BRP operating on the DAM.

The remuneration for industries follows an implicit scheme, complemented by the BRP offering an aggregated product to optimize his portfolio on the DAM, similarly to an explicit DR programme. Whereas operationally, DIF requires prior notification similar to explicit DR, with day-ahead schedule declaration. But, similarly to implicit schemes, no bid size requirements are imposed.

The determination of DIF activation costs begins with an industry-specific analysis of each customer, starting with on-site visits to assess production processes and constraints. Iterative Q&A sessions with production planners and engineers were carried out, identifying key costs related to the electricity demand. Notably, production stop duration, additional resources consumption during long and short term stops and personnel costs were modeled and associated to the possible DIF profiles. Once these factors are identified, a production process model is developed to generate baseline and DIF schedules. It should be noted that these costs are not simply proportional to energy consumption but reflect other setup expenses, inefficiencies, and operational constraints. This procedure was conducted within the FLEX4FACT [47] project, where case studies provided realistic activation cost data. While the full methodology is beyond the scope of this paper, the data used here originates from these assessments.

C. BRP COST OPTIMIZATION

1) MILP OPTIMIZATION PROBLEM FORMULATION

Having defined both the algorithm to forecast DAM electricity prices and the rules of industrial flexibility, the BRP portfolio optimization with day-ahead flexibility activation can be defined. A MILP problem is formulated, to detect the best configuration of DIFs according to the predicted electricity costs. All the computations are conducted using the Pyomo library and the GNU Linear Programming Kit (GLPK) open-source solver [53]. The problem is formalized considering the following assumptions:

- **Unrestricted DAM Purchase:** The BRP can purchase electricity at the DAM price without market energy volume constraints or penalties.
- **Demand Fulfilment Requirement:** The BRP portfolio's demand must be met at all times.
- **Predefined DIF Information:** DIFs and their activation costs are known and quantifiable before optimization, ensuring information availability and transparency.
- **Fixed Consumption Patterns:** Electricity demand and DIF consumption patterns are assumed to match

declared values, considering only a day-ahead scenario and disregarding intra-day variations.

- **Absence of Grid Constraints:** No grid constraints or transmission limitations are considered, and congestion analysis due to flexibility volumes is out of scope.

The problem is defined considering the following indexes:

$t = 1, \dots, T$ index over hourly time intervals;

$i = 1, \dots, n$ index over different factories;

$j = 1, \dots, m$ index over the possible DIFs of each factory.

It is assumed that all industries offer m DIFs.

The optimization variables of the problem are defined in Table 1.

TABLE 1. Optimization problem variables.

Variable	Domain	Description
P_t (MW)	Real	Power purchased by the BRP from the grid
x_{ij} (-)	Binary	Identifier of DIF activation

The objective function, which minimizes the costs of the BRP portfolio in € is defined in equation 1.

$$\min(\text{OBJ}) : \sum_{t=1}^T P_t \hat{\pi}_t \Delta t + \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m \alpha \phi_{ij} x_{ij} \quad (1)$$

where $\hat{\pi}_t$ represents the hourly predicted DAM electricity price, Δt is the time interval, in this case 1 hour and ϕ_{ij} represents the cost of activation the DIF offer j of factory i . The dimensionless parameter α represents the flexibility cost multiplier. It is used to carry out a sensitivity analysis to evaluate how the model performs for different ranges of flexibility activation costs.

In addition to the objective function, the constraints of the optimization problem are defined. For each industry only one DIF profile can be activated, indicated by the binary variable x_{ij} . This is expressed by equation 2.

$$\sum_{j=1}^m x_{ij} = 1 \quad (2)$$

$i = 1, \dots, n$

The electricity demand of the industrial customers of the BRP should be satisfied at all times. Hence, the constraint shown in equation 3 is defined.

$$P_t = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m P_{ijt} x_{ij} \quad (3)$$

$t = 1, \dots, T$

where P_{ijt} represents the hourly electricity consumption of DIF j of industry i at time t . If $j=0$ for all of the i industries, then the total purchased power by the BRP from the grid is denoted as P_t^{BASE} , indicating the Baseline scenario.

2) SCALABILITY OF THE OPTIMIZATION MODEL FOR LARGER PORTFOLIOS

The scalability of the optimization model was evaluated to assess performance when applied to larger portfolios of industrial customers. Being the time window fixed to the 24 hours of the day-ahead, the time horizon does not impact computational performance, and the only parameters that affect the computational time are n and m . Thus, the scalability of the model was assessed by measuring the runtime $\tau_{runtime}$ for varying numbers of industries and flexibility profiles, using equation 4.

$$\tau_{runtime} = \tau_{end} - \tau_{start} \quad (4)$$

where τ_{start} and τ_{end} denote the timestamps before and after the optimization, respectively. The experiments were conducted on hardware equipped with an Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-10510U CPU @ 1.80GHz processor with a base clock speed of 2.30GHz and 16 GB of RAM.

3) SERVICE PERFORMANCE METRICS

To evaluate the total costs of the BRP portfolio and the feasibility of the proposed strategy, economic metrics are evaluated before and after optimization considering both predicted and held out validation data. Equation 5 is used to compute the real costs of the BRP portfolio electricity consumption C^{BASE} , considering the Baseline scenario and the real electricity price. Intuitively, by using the predicted price $\hat{\pi}_t$, the predicted BRP portfolio costs before optimization \hat{C}^{BASE} are obtained.

$$C^{BASE} = \sum_{t=1}^T P_t^{BASE} \pi_t \Delta t \quad (5)$$

After optimization, the BRP electricity purchase costs are evaluated in a similar manner. Considering real electricity prices, the predicted optimal BRP portfolio costs C^{OPT} can be obtained using Equation 6. This metric represents an *ex-post* financial evaluation of the strategy. Specifically, P_t is obtained from the day-ahead optimization based on forecasted DAM prices and is subsequently multiplied by the real electricity price π_t . This calculation reflects the costs incurred by the BRP when industries activate the DIFs recommended by the optimization model.

Equation 6 is also used to compute the predicted BRP electricity purchase costs \hat{C}^{OPT} when the predicted electricity price $\hat{\pi}_t$ is used instead of the real price.

$$C^{OPT} = \sum_{t=1}^T P_t \pi_t \Delta t \quad (6)$$

By verifying whether the DIFs determined by the cost minimization model yield positive returns even when using real price values, the validity of the developed service can be assessed in real operating scenarios. Finally, the savings S and predicted savings \hat{S} are computed as difference between the

costs before and after optimization, as shown in equation 7.

$$S = C^{BASE} - C^{OPT} \quad (7)$$

Emissions corresponding to the BRP portfolio electricity consumption for one day of operation after optimization G^{OPT} and before G^{BASE} are computed using equations 8 and 9 respectively, both measured in t_{CO_2} . $\theta_t^{CO_2}$ represents the CO_2 emissions associated to real time grid electricity generation and is measured in t_{CO_2}/MWh [54].

$$G^{OPT} = \sum_{t=1}^T \theta_t^{CO_2} P_t \Delta t \quad (8)$$

$$G^{BASE} = \sum_{t=1}^T \theta_t^{CO_2} P_t^{BASE} \Delta t \quad (9)$$

And their difference allows to defined the net emissions savings R^{CO_2} , as shown in equation 10

$$R^{CO_2} = G^{BASE} - G^{OPT} \quad (10)$$

III. CASE STUDY

A. ELECTRICITY PRICE DATA

The case study is located in Spain, and the data for the target DAM electricity price are collected from publicly available records of the information system of the Spanish system operator ESIOS [55]. The data have hourly granularity and they range from 01/01/2016 to 10/02/2022. The electricity price shows tight correlation to socio-economic events, with a noticeable trend disruption in 2020, following the Covid-19 pandemic [56]. Subsequently in 2021, following the increase of gas prices and geopolitical instabilities, the electricity prices soar to historical maximums [57]. Fig. 3 shows the full dataset of the target variable, highlighting training and testing splits, as well as the chosen sample day considered for this study.

FIGURE 3. DAM marginal price historical data.

Further analysing the evidenced trend disruption in the period ranging from beginning of 2021 until the end of the dataset in 2022, Fig. 4 shows the KDE plot. It represents the probability density function of the target variables before and after 2021, to visualise changes in distribution before and after the energy crisis. For the electricity price a change from a mean of 46.24 €/MWh to 121.05 €/MWh and standard deviation from 15.05 €/MWh to 76.9 €/MWh. Visually it

FIGURE 4. DAM marginal price KDE plot.

can be seen as it is narrowly centered around a low price value between 2016 and 2020 and, after 2021 a higher and more volatile price is detected. The increase in volatility and change of trend of the electricity price might affect model performance, but also should make over-fitting easier to detect.

Following the feature selection technique mentioned in section II-A, the final set to train the model is narrowed down to the ones shown in table 2.

TABLE 2. Day-ahead electricity price input features.

Typology	Input feature	Source
Calendar	Hour of the day, day of the week, work day.	-
Target variable lags	Electricity price shifted by 36, 48, 72, 96 and 168 hours.	[58]
Electricity generation mix	Wind, Solar, Nuclear, Combined Cycle Gas Turbine (CCGT) generation, CO_2 free generation percentage.	[59]–[63]
System demand	Total demand, residual demand.	[64], [65]
Daily gas price lags	Gas price shifted by 24, 48, 72 and 168 hours.	[66]

The features are selected and engineered to improve the predictive power of the model. Calendar features are critical to detect periodic patterns, such as hourly recurrent values or the fact that prices are typically lower on weekends. Target variable lags also allow to take in account temporal dependencies. Information on the electricity generation mix can indicate whether expensive or cheap generation units are being used, thus affecting the price. System demand is correlated to higher prices, especially during periods in which renewable supply is low. Daily gas prices lags incorporate in the model the most recent available information on the prices of an important fuel source for electricity generation, especially following the Europe energy crisis [67].

B. BRP PORTFOLIO DATA

Electricity consumption data are shared by a BRP operating in the Spanish autonomous community of Catalunya. It provides a dataset of hourly electricity consumption, measured at the grid access points. The portfolio comprises various

clients, with a peak power consumption of 69 MW for the chosen sample day.

The DIF framework for BRPs remains largely consistent across countries participating in Single Day-Ahead Coupling (SDAC) [68]. Indeed, focusing on DAM operation all the countries within the SDAC geographical scope follow the same EU Pan-European Hybrid Electricity Market Integration Algorithm (EUPHEMIA) [69], all having market gate closure for bid submission at 12:00 CET, compatibly with the forecasting algorithm presented in this paper. The forecasting window, however, should be adapted for BRPs operating in the United Kingdom and Switzerland, where gate closure is at 11:00 GMT and 11:00 CET respectively.

FIGURE 5. BRP portfolio composition with baseline production schedules.

The dataset includes both the total aggregated electricity consumption of the BRP portfolio and, for the selected sample day of 26/4/2021, synthetic baseline consumption profiles for the six largest industrial customers within the portfolio. These six customers, denoted as F1 through F6, represent distinct industries with varying consumption characteristics and flexibility capabilities. The exact nature of their industrial processes is not given, as it is assumed the aggregator does not require operational details of the specifics of the manufacturing processes. However, each customer provides with full transparency Baseline, DIF profiles and the respective activation costs. The flexibility strategy proposed in this study is developed specifically for these six flexible consumers (F1-F6), while the remainder of the BRP portfolio is assumed to follow its baseline consumption profile and is treated as non-flexible load. Fig. 5 showcases the de-aggregation of the BRP portfolio, according to the information shared. Table 3 summarizes key information on the consumption of each industry.

TABLE 3. Industrial energy consumption data.

	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
Peak Consumption (MW)	8.33	8.33	18.33	10	13.75	8.75
Daily Energy Demand (MWh)	92.5	81.67	210.83	85.83	330	90.42

As explained in section II-B, industries are required to submit their baseline electricity consumption alongside with

a set of m DIFs. This is shown graphically for each of the industrial customers in Fig. 6. It can be noticed that the shape of the electricity demand profile changes significantly, but the daily energy consumption remains unchanged for each factory. Completing the information of the DIFs offers, the activation costs ϕ_{ij} are shown in Table 4.

TABLE 4. DIFs activation costs measured in €/day.

	Base	DIF1	DIF2	DIF3	DIF4	DIF5	DIF6
Factory 1	0	216	246	156	90	174	186
Factory 2	0	84	240	60	102	168	102
Factory 3	0	342	306	72	294	84	108
Factory 4	0	360	342	114	138	348	330
Factory 5	0	84	294	216	114	324	78
Factory 6	0	126	180	156	192	354	336

Introduced in section II-C3, the hourly values for the emission associated to real time grid electricity generation $\theta_t^{CO_2}$ are shown in Fig. 7. A mean of $0.119 \text{ tCO}_2/\text{MWh}$ and a standard deviation of $0.042 \text{ tCO}_2/\text{MWh}$ are recorded over the considered period.

IV. RESULTS

This section presents the results obtained for the system under study. Using the electricity price forecasting models, predictions are generated for the entire testing period from 18/02/2021 to 10/02/2022. To assess model performance, a representative week (26/04/2021 - 02/05/2021) is selected, where 168 hourly forecasts from each model are compared against held-out validation data.

Based on these predictions, the BRP portfolio optimization problem is solved. A detailed analysis is first conducted for a specific sample day (26/04/2021), where the impact of varying the flexibility activation cost, controlled by parameter α , is examined to assess the robustness of the proposed method.

Finally, the study of the service's performance is extended to the entire testing period, including a sensitivity analysis varying α . Since BRP portfolio demand data is limited, only the available observations are used, while all available daily price forecasts for the testing period are considered. This allows for an assessment of how electricity price forecasting errors influence the optimization strategy over time.

A. DAY-AHEAD ELECTRICITY PRICE FORECASTING

As defined in section II-A, the models are fitted on the training data, tuning the hyper-parameters using grid search with cross validation. The values used are shown in Table 5.

The electricity price is computed with each algorithm, and compared with test data, as shown in Fig. 8. As it can be observed, all the models are able to predict the target variables with good accuracy. Daily and weekly trends are recognized in both cases, with an accurate estimation of the magnitude and detection of the periods of peaks and valleys. During the workdays (between 26/04 and 30/04) the outputs of the three models present negligible differences. During

FIGURE 6. Possible DIFs for each industry.

FIGURE 7. Hourly emission intensity of Spanish grid electricity generation for the chosen testing period.

TABLE 5. Best hyper-parameters of the different models.

Model	Hyper-parameter	Value
MLR	-	-
SVR	C	150
	Gamma	0.01
	Kernel	linear
MLP	N° of layers	2
	Neurons in first layer	3
	Neurons in second layer	3
	Activation function	ReLU
	Learning rate	0.001
	L2 regularization term	0.01

this period, the target variable is slightly under estimated, particularly in the first hours of 27/04 and 30/04. On the weekend, a larger difference can be appreciated between the predictions of the three algorithms, nonetheless they are all able to predict the price dip of Saturday 01/05. MLP slightly underestimates the real value, with MLR being the closest. All three models fail to detect the magnitude of the valley on the early hours of Sunday 02/05.

Table 6 shows the performance of the fitted models, considering different testing periods. It is noticeable a

FIGURE 8. Electricity price predictions for the sample week with different algorithms.

difference in the error metrics as the time period of interest increases. For the chosen sample day the MAE and RMSE have a lower value compared to the full time period, likely due to the change of trend and increase of electricity prices recorded in the following months. Inversely, the coefficient of correlation improves as the sample size increases. For the sample week and sample day the three algorithms have similar metrics, with MLR being the best performing one by a small margin. However, considering the full period, MLP performs best in all the computed error metrics. MLP, thus, is the chosen model to provide DAM price forecasts to be used in the BRP portfolio optimization.

Further analysing the three models, Fig. 9 shows the scatter plots of predicted data against testing data, with the ideal case of perfect match between predicted and real data highlighted by the red line. All three models exhibit a strong correlation between predictions and actual values, with no signs of overfitting. Notably, the scatter plots of the MLR and SVR models appear highly similar, suggesting that both models recognize the linear structure of the data in a comparable manner.

FIGURE 9. Comparison between observed and predicted electricity prices for MLR, SVR and MLP. The ideal case of perfect predictions is denoted with a red line.

Nonetheless, difference between these two is captured by the error metrics of Table 6.

TABLE 6. Performance of the forecasting models over different time periods.

Period	Model	MAE (€/MWh)	RMSE (€/MWh)	R ² (-)
Sample Day	MLR	3.18	4.2	0.29
	SVR	3.51	4.56	0.27
	MLP	3.71	4.56	0.27
Sample Week	MLR	3.93	5.10	0.74
	SVR	4.21	5.24	0.73
	MLP	4.59	5.60	0.69
Full Period	MLR	15.84	25.61	0.89
	SVR	15.48	25.67	0.87
	MLP	13.00	21.70	0.92

The error distribution plot shown in Fig. 10 demonstrates that the chosen MLP model has good accuracy and low bias. The figure displays the histogram of the errors measured as the difference between real values and predictions. In the plot they are separated in discrete bins, alongside a smoothed KDE curve and highlights of the mean prediction error of 1.20 €/MWh and the median of 3.53 €/MWh. The unimodal and symmetric shape of the error distribution suggests that most forecasts closely match actual electricity prices, with limited extreme deviations. The relatively sharp peak in the density plot further confirms that the majority of errors remain within a narrow range, further proving the model's reliability. While some large errors are present, they occur infrequently.

FIGURE 10. DAM Electricity price forecasting error distribution using the MLP model.

B. BRP PORTFOLIO OPTIMIZATION

1) SAMPLE DAY RESULTS

Solving the cost optimization model of the BRP portfolio for the chosen sample day, the production profiles to be followed by each industry in order to minimize portfolio energy costs are identified. This is shown in Table 7.

TABLE 7. Optimal production profiles and relative activation costs.

	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
Profile	Baseline	DIF 3	DIF 6	Baseline	Baseline	DIF 4
Cost (€)	0	60	108	0	0	192

Some of the industries deviate from their baseline electricity consumption profile, highlighting potential for cost reduction thanks to the implementation of the strategy. The final consumption schedule of the considered sample day are shown visually in Fig. 11. While F1, F4 and F5 do not deviate from the Baseline, F2, F3 and F6 do. F2 and F6 offer a DIF with higher consumption during the central hours of the day, avoiding evening price peak, whereas the optimal DIF activated by F3 has a higher consumption during the first hours of the day. F1, F4 and F5 do not activate DIFs meaning that their electricity consumption remains unchanged. This suggests that either their baseline consumption already aligns with electricity price trends or that operational constraints prevent them from adopting more optimal DIF profiles.

Figure 12 provides a comprehensive view of the BRP portfolio after optimization, showing both non-flexible load and the consumption of the different factories throughout the day. Compared with the BRP load composition shown in figure 5, consumption is higher during night hours, when electricity prices are lower.

Table 8 provides a summary of the performance metrics of the service for the sample day, calculated using equations 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10. The scenarios of the BRP portfolio with and without DIFs optimization for both the predicted and real cases are considered. As the non-flexible share of the BRP portfolio remains unchanged before and after optimization, it is excluded from the computation of these metrics.

FIGURE 11. Optimal DIF of each industry compared to the Baseline.

FIGURE 12. BRP portfolio composition after day-ahead optimization.

TABLE 8. Service performance for the chosen sample day: predicted vs real scenario.

	Predicted		Real	
	Baseline	Optimized	Baseline	Optimized
C (k€)	65.199	64.476	67.788	67.698
S (k€)	-	0.722	-	0.092
S (%)	-	1.09	-	0.13
G (t_{CO_2})	112.09	112.39	112.09	112.39
R^{CO_2} (t_{CO_2})	-	-0.3	-	-0.3

Firstly, by comparing predicted and real cost before optimization (\widehat{C}^{BASE} and C^{BASE}) it is noticeable that the first slightly underestimate the second one. This is a consequence of the underestimation of the predicted prices, evidenced in the previous section. Optimized costs are, thus, also lower when considering predicted prices as opposed to real prices.

Secondly, net positive savings can be achieved by introducing flexible schedules through DIFs, both in the real and predicted scenarios, despite the additional activation costs. For the studied day, savings of 1.09% are observed with predicted prices, while 0.13% is achieved with real electricity

prices. Notably, the fact that the real optimized scenario still results in positive, albeit marginal, savings confirms an improved alignment between consumption and market prices. This demonstrates that DIFs optimized based on predicted prices effectively help the BRP reduce its portfolio costs.

Finally, it can be observed that remissions remain almost constant, with a minor increase of 0.3 t_{CO_2} after optimization. They do not depend from the electricity price, but only from the profile of the consumption. Thus, they are equal in both the predicted and real scenario. It may seem negative that following the strategy leads to slightly higher emissions. For this reason a full analysis of the testing period is conducted in subsection IV-B2 to determine whether this is an isolated occurrence or a recurring trend.

To assess the impact of flexibility activation costs on the optimization strategy, a sensitivity analysis is performed by varying the dimensionless cost multiplier parameter α . A range of α values from 0 to 6 is considered, with increments of 0.25. For each value, the sample day optimization is carried out, providing insights into how different flexibility activation costs influence the strategy's outcomes. This analysis helps to determine the conditions under which industries are more or less likely to activate flexibility.

Figure 13 illustrates the number of industrial customers choosing to activate flexibility for different α values. The plot clearly shows that as activation costs increase, fewer industries opt for flexibility. When α is greater than 4.5, no industries activate flexibility, whereas for α values of 0.25 or lower, all industries deviate from the baseline. The figure also highlights the benchmark scenario, denoted with $\bar{\alpha}$ corresponding to $\alpha = 1$, as well as notable values of α , denoted as $\alpha_0, \alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_6$. α_0 and α_6 represent the first and last values of the range considered, while the others represent the values of α that induce a change in number of flexibilities activated. These notable values of α are shown in Table 9.

TABLE 9. Notable values of α identified in the sensitivity analysis.

α_0	α_1	α_2	α_3	α_4	α_5	α_6	$\bar{\alpha}$
0	0.25	0.75	2.25	2.5	4.5	6	1

Figure 14 illustrates how total costs evolve as α varies, distinguishing between the predicted and real cost scenarios. First, considering the scenario where the optimized DIFs are multiplied by predicted electricity prices, the ‘‘Optimized predicted cost’’ curve increases monotonically until α_5 . Beyond this point, no flexibility is activated, which makes the costs before and after optimization identical. In particular, the benchmark scenario of $\bar{\alpha}$ results in significantly lower costs compared to higher α values, emphasizing the benefit of flexibility activation, in a case where forecasting errors of the electricity prices are not taken into account.

In the real cost scenario, where real electricity prices are applied to the optimized DIF profiles, the trend is no longer strictly monotonic. This highlights the impact of electricity price forecasting errors on the strategy’s performance. In certain α ranges, costs decrease despite an increasing activation cost, indicating that suboptimal flexibility combinations are being selected due to forecast inaccuracies. However, this is expected, as perfect electricity price forecasting is impossible. Albeit marginal, the benchmark scenario shows an improvement of the BRP portfolio’s costs, as also shown in Table 8.

FIGURE 13. Number of industrial customers activating DIFs for different values of α .

Completing the analysis of the execution of the algorithm for the chosen sample day, Table 10 shows the computational runtime $\tau_{runtime}$ for increasing number of industries and DIF profiles considered. For the considered case study ($n=6, m=6$), the computational time stays under 0.2 seconds. For the largest case analysed ($n=200, m=200$) the recorded runtime reaches 45.54 seconds. Despite the non-linear increase, the runtime remains within acceptable limits for the purposes of the applicability of the strategy.

FIGURE 14. BRP portfolio costs before and after optimization for different values of α , for real and predicted prices scenarios.

TABLE 10. Runtime results for different combinations of n and m .

(n, m)	(6, 6)	(20, 20)	(100, 100)	(200, 200)
$\tau_{runtime}$ (s)	0.187	0.398	8.943	45.54

2) FULL TESTING PERIOD ANALYSIS

The sample day analysis provided insights into flexibility activation and its impact on costs. However, to assess the long-term reliability of the strategy and the effects of electricity price forecasting errors, a broader analysis is conducted over the full testing period (18/02/2021 to 10/02/2021).

As seen in Table 8, the savings achieved for the sample day in the post-optimization scenario amounted to only 0.9 k€, corresponding to 0.13% of the total industrial customer costs for that day. While this represents a positive outcome, it is important to determine whether the strategy can be more effective if different days are considered. To achieve this, the optimization model is executed for all days within the testing period while, considering the values of α shown in Table 9.

By computing the daily real savings (using Equation 7) for all days in the testing period, a KDE plot was generated to analyze the distribution of savings across different α values. This visualization helps to assess how the flexibility activation cost influences the overall economic performance of the strategy. Similarly to the analysis conducted for the sample day, the KDE plot reveals a clear trend: lower α values correspond to higher savings, as lower activation costs encourage more industrial customers to participate in demand flexibility. Conversely, as α increases, fewer customers activate flexibility, leading to smaller cost reductions. However, it is important to note that even for the most favorable case of α_0 , some occurrences of negative savings are observed, due to electricity price forecasting errors. Despite these occasional suboptimal cases, the mean savings remain positive for all α values, indicating that the strategy consistently delivers cost reductions over the long term.

The characterization of these distributions is complemented in Table 12, which presents the mean (μ) and standard deviation (σ) of real savings for all considered α values, with the benchmark $\bar{\alpha}$ highlighted.

In addition to savings, the table also provides insights into the distribution of emissions reductions, computed for each day of the testing period using Equation 10. The results confirm that the strategy effectively reduces emissions, as the mean emissions savings remain positive across all values of α , even for higher activation costs. This indicates that, on average, the optimized profiles successfully align electricity consumption with periods of lower carbon intensity, contributing to a more sustainable energy usage.

The last two columns describe the number of deviations, representing the number of industrial customers opting to activate flexibility. As expected, the mean number of deviations decreases for higher α values, reinforcing the trend observed in previous figures: as flexibility activation costs increase, fewer industries choose to adjust their consumption profiles.

FIGURE 15. Real daily savings distribution over the full testing period for different values of α .

Completing the full testing period analysis, using equations 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 and summing over all the days of the testing period, the Table 11 is obtained, considering $\alpha = 1$. It is reinforced the concept that the strategy is useful in lowering costs and emissions. Comparing with Table 8 it is interesting to see that the percentage savings for the real scenario are 1.96% as opposed to the low value of 0.13% measured for the sample day. Furthermore, emissions savings are also recorded, with a reduction of 276.69 t_{CO_2} corresponding to a reduction of 0.74% of emissions associated to the electricity consumption of the industrial flexible customers of the BRP over the full testing period. Overall, these findings reinforce the notion that demand flexibility not only provides economic benefits but also contributes to emissions reductions, with the magnitude of these benefits depending on the cost assigned to activating flexibility.

TABLE 11. Full testing period results of day-ahead flexibility service performance: predicted vs real scenario.

	Predicted		Real	
	Baseline	Optimized	Baseline	Optimized
C (k€)	41516.74	40861.51	41997.52	41172.60
S (k€)	-	655.22	-	824.91
S (%)	-	1.58	-	1.96
$G(t_{CO_2})$	37447.63	37170.94	37447.63	37170.94
$R^{CO_2}(t_{CO_2})$	-	276.69	-	276.69

TABLE 12. Mean and standard deviation of savings, emissions, and deviations across alphas.

	S (k€)		R^{CO_2} (t_{CO_2})		N. Deviations (-)	
	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ
α_0	3268	3635	0.73	2.18	5.69	0.58
α_1	2982	3612	0.74	2.13	5.43	0.87
α_2	2491	3520	0.79	2.08	4.33	1.19
α_3	1656	3078	0.64	1.73	2.55	1.47
α_4	1570	2992	0.62	1.66	2.31	1.43
α_5	1100	2577	0.43	1.37	1.32	1.05
α_6	947	2451	0.41	1.26	0.97	0.91
$\bar{\alpha}$	2311	3444	0.78	2.04	3.95	1.29

V. CONCLUSION

This study presented a day-ahead service to minimize BRP electricity portfolio costs, providing a quantitative example based on the case study of a Catalan BRP. The concept of DIF was introduced as a means of improving the provision of industrial flexibility at a reasonable cost while complying with the scheduling needs of manufacturing processes. This allowed to formulate a MILP optimization model to minimize costs on the DAM integrated with DAM electricity price forecasts.

Firstly, it is found that, out of the ones analysed, the MLP algorithm is the most suited to accurately predict the day-ahead electricity price. By including features describing the electricity generation mix as well as the daily gas prices, it is possible to create a reliable model despite the volatility of the DAM electricity price. Over the full testing period of more than one year, R^2 of 0.92 was achieved.

Then, solving the formulated BRP cost optimization problem, DIF offers are prompted to be activated to minimize the objective function. Half of studied flexible customers of the BRP portfolio deviate from baseline schedule despite the additional costs to do so. Indeed, the results showcase a potential application of the proposed concept of DIF and day-ahead portfolio management techniques, mentioned but not explored in literature.

Finally, the financial outcomes are presented. A scenario using only predicted data is compared with the case of the application of the computed DIF with real testing data. The values obtained are similar in the two cases, confirming the accuracy of the model. Over the full testing period, savings of 1.96% of the BRP energy purchased costs on the DAM are achieved by following the proposed model, demonstrating a successful implementation of the flexibility strategy.

Results suggest that integrating flexibility strategies could incentivize greater participation of industrial consumers in energy markets. This offers a pathway toward more resilient and integrated energy systems.

While this study highlights the benefits of incorporating DIFs into day-ahead management, further research is needed to generalize these findings across different markets and industrial sectors. Refining forecasting algorithms and improving the definition of DIF offers could enhance the model's robustness.

Future work should focus on incorporating stochastic elements into the optimization framework to better account for uncertainties in electricity prices, demand fluctuations, and flexibility availability. By integrating probabilistic models, the strategy could become more resilient to unexpected variations, leading to more reliable and cost-effective decision-making. Additionally, expanding the approach to include intra-day markets would enable real-time flexibility optimization, allowing adjustments based on updated forecasts and market conditions. This would improve the reactivity of the strategy, ensuring that flexibility activation remains cost-efficient and aligned with actual system needs.

Further research should also explore regulatory barriers for BRPs across different countries and assess the scalability of the proposed flexibility mechanisms in larger energy portfolios. Addressing these aspects will help bridge the gap between theory and real-world implementation.

In conclusion, this study demonstrates that combining DIF with day-ahead optimization can yield substantial cost savings, while improving industrial customer participation in flexibility provision. The findings offer a sample case study for industries to adopt more flexible energy management strategies, showcasing cost reduction opportunities on the day-ahead via BRP portfolio optimization.

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